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Original Research Report

Hair Growth Promotion Skills for Hair Dressers and Nutrition Requirements for Hair Growth of Females in Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study focuses on hair growth promotion skills for hair dressers and nutrition requirements for hair growth of females in Umunneochi local government area (LGA) of Abia State. Specifically, the study aimed to examine the practices that promote human hair growth, assess the importance of human hair growth, determine the effect of poor nutrition on hair and identify the skills of hairdressers to promote hair growth. The study adopted a descriptive research design. Population for the study was 2,800. Sample for the study was 200 using a multistage sampling techniques involving simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using mean. The result of the study examined six practices that promote human hair growth, six importance of human hair, eight effects of poor nutrition on hair and eleven hairdressers' skills were identified. It was suggested that adolescents and mothers should be encouraged to eat recommended diets to suit their age; they should maintain a good hairdresser; and they should consult a dermatologist at regular intervals and follow their advice.

Keywords: Dermatologist, Good nutrition, Hair growth, Hairdressing, Hairdressers

1. Introduction

Hair is one of the greatest assets of an individual. Jackson (2014) views hair of human as a marvelous tool which an individual can express her sexuality and how she feels about herself. In fact, many see it as the most noticeable feminine structure. Hair is often a physical expression one's sense of self, of a desire to present oneself to and amongst a community, of social status and roles, and of cultural values (Johnson, 1997). For many people, hair is a form of self-expression (Clayton, 2014). Daniel (2015) describes hair as an outgrowth of filamentous cells, containing keratin that grows from the follicles found in the dermis. According to him, the human body apart from the palms of the hands and soles of the feet is covered in follicles which produce thick terminal and fine values hair. The presence of hair on the skin is a distinctive mammalian characteristics. The development of hair which begins in the third month of full fetal life is prefaced by the down growth of thickened cells of the epidermis into the underlying dermis and connective tissue. According to Ross and Wilson (2016), the hair is the result of a multiplication of cells that clump together to produce a papilla at the base of the follicle. Constantly dividing these cells push upwards towards the surface, becoming impregnated with the protein keratin, to form the hair shaft. According to Jablonski (2013), the hair shaft in cross-section can be divided roughly into three zones. Starting from the outside, the cuticle protects the inner structure of the hair) which consists of several layers of flat, thin walls laid out like roof singles; the cortex (responsible for providing hair its structure) contain the keratin bundles in cell structure that remain roughly rod like and in some cases, the medulla (for hair elasticity) a disorganized and open area at the fibre centre.

Hair grows because of the continued division of these “matrix” cells. The scalp alone is covered with up to two million hairs growing about 0.3mm a day. Boulos et al. (2013) informs that the knowledge about the structure of the hair will help to guide on how to keep hair shiny and healthy. It is necessary to understand the qualities of the hair that is healthy as this knowledge will help to understand what care one should always give to make it healthy. Leena (2017) describes the characteristics of a healthy hair which is smooth texture and feel, shining, holds curls, relatively easy to comb. A lot of care is needed for one's hair to be healthy, silky and Lustrous. Saroini (2016) opines that to maintain the hair, good nutrition and other details of healthy living should be maintained. It is necessary to take proper care of the hair. Good nutrition and health are closely aligned and interrelated. The healthy benefits of one factor affect the positive outcomes in the other. Nutritional guidelines for a healthy diet is a means of preventing the problems. A healthy diet involves consuming appropriate amount of all essential nutrients and adequate amount of water. Adequate water will help replenish the body's water lost through sweat and urination. Alcohol should be among the first things to skip in your diet. Eat the right amount of food to maintain a healthy lifestyle. Cobb (2016) also explains that for the hair to be well cared for a healthy supply of fruits and vegetables, whole grain and foods rich in calcium and protein are not only appealing but highly nutritious. Taking care of one's hair restores colour, increases hair density and regains elasticity of the scalp and increases self-confidence. So, proper diet coupled with right hair care products coupled with right application of hair dressing skills will result in lustrous hair. Skill is a well-established habit of doing something and it involves acquisition of performance capabilities. Practically speaking, hair dressing skills involve the ability to determine the right hair texture, select the right relaxer, determine time of the relax hair, determine various hair styles, manipulates the hairdressing equipment, among others. Thus, the combination of skills and knowledge involved in the profession if adopted by females could serve as palliative measures for this hard time.

1.1. Statement of Problem

It is something of note that if hair is not properly maintained it provokes anxiety in any one when it starts thinning, falling and disappearing (Ako, 2018). Boulos et al. (2013) believes that hair has problems if it is not properly taken care of. In their own view, some common problems of the hair such as falling hair will result. Rodney (2016) adds hair damages, severe scalp infection or hair disease. All these hair diseases or problems when chronic, lead to irreversible hair loss.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine Hair growth promotion skills for hairdressers and nutrition requirement for growth for females in Umunneochi LGA, Abia State. Specifically, the study;

- (a) Examined the practices that promote human hair growth.
- (b) Access the importance of human hair.
- (c) Determine the effect of poor nutrition on the hair.
- (d) Identify the skills for hairdressers to promote growth.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the practices that promote human hair growth?
- (b) What are the importance of human hair?
- (c) What are the effects of poor nutrition on the hair?
- (d) What are the skills for hairdressers?

2. Materials and Methods

1.1. Design for the Study

The study adopted a survey research design. It sought information from females, their opinion and attitudes. This was to collect relevant information on analysis of the selected information for promoting human hair growth among females through good nutrition maintenance. It was calculated from answers elicited from respondents through questions.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The ethical clearance for this research was received from the College of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria. All respondents gave their informed consent before completing the questionnaire.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was carried out among females in Umunneochi LGA which comprises of Nneato, Isuochi and Umuchieze. It remained a study area since relevant foods. It is one of the food baskets in the south-East. It has a lot to eat that can nourish the body or hair.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for the study was made up of two groups of people such as adolescents and mothers from the two geo-political zones (Nneato and Isuochi). An estimated population of 1500 adolescents and 1300 mothers were used for the study summing up to 2,800 in number. Multistage random sampling technique was employed in the selection of adolescents (12-18 years) and mothers 35-40 years for the study. Two geopolitical zones namely Nneato and Isuochi were randomly

selected in the first stage form among the three geo-political zones. The two geo-political zones have 15 wards and 16 wards respectively. In the second wards and 16 wards respectively. From each of the ward, participants were selected randomly to arrive at a sample size of 200.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was constructed using a four-point Likert scale to guide the responses. The questionnaire items were generated based on the information gathered from review of related literature. It contained 200 questions and was face validated by experts in related field, t-test reliability was used to test the reliability of the instrument.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

A total of 200 copies were distributed by hand to subjects who made up the sample. After administration, 200 were completed, duly filled and retrieved directly from respondents.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Any item that had a mean score of 2.50 and above was interpreted as 'agree' items whose mean fell below 2.50 were considered as "disagree".

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean of the responses of Adolescents and Mothers on practices that promote human hair growth.

S/N	Promoting of human hair growth	X ₁	X ₂	X _g	Remark
1	Take plenty of fruits and vegetables	3.14	2.84	3.49	Agree
2.	Eat foods rich in protein	3.56	3.55	3.56	Agree
3.	Take whole grain and foods rich in calcium	3.29	3.11	3.20	Agree
4.	Keep hair healthy and shining	3.64	3.56	3.60	Agree
5.	Minimize intake of alcohol	3.88	3.84	3.86	Agree
6.	Apply a good hair cream	3.55	3.66	3.07	Agree

X₁ = Mean of female adolescents between the ages of 12-18 years

X₂ = Mean of mothers (40-50)

X_g = grand Mean

In Table 1, it was revealed that all the adolescents and mothers agreed to all the items listed. All the items had mean ratings above 3.50. This implies that all these items listed were reflective on promoting human hair growth.

Table 2: Mean ratings on the importance of human hair by Adolescents and mothers

S/N	The importance of human hair	X ₁	X ₂	X _g	Remark
1	Beautifies oneself	3.86	3.82	3.33	Agree
2.	Adds height	3.55	3.56	3.56	Agree
3.	Shows class of human being	3.44	3.78	3.61	Agree
4.	Indicate taste	3.74	3.68	3.71	Agree

5.	Shows personality of an individual	3.52	3.58	3.68	Agree
6.	Shows the state of health	3.42	3.56	3.55	Agree

X_1 = Mean of female adolescents between the ages of 12-18 years

X_2 = Mean of mothers (40-50)

X_g = grand Mean

In Table 2, it was revealed that the adolescents between 12-18 years and mothers agreed to all the items listed. Mean responses of the respondents showed that all the items had mean scores above 2.50 which was the criterion level of acceptance. This means that the importance of hair were identified by these Adolescents and mothers.

Table 3: Mean ratings on the effect of poor nutrition on the hair

S/N	The effect of poor nutrition on the hair	X1	X2	Xg	Remarks
i.	Thinning	2.72	2.72	2.72	Agree
2.	Falling	3.36	3.29	3.33	Agree
3.	Disappearing	2.84	3.11	2.91	Agree
4.	Dandruff	2.29	2.36	2.33	Disagree
5.	Hair damages	2.68	2.74	2.71	Agree
6.	Severe Scalp infection	3.86	3.29	3.33	Agree
7.	Irreversible hair loss	3.86	3.82	3.46	Agree
8.	Visible split ends	2.84	3.11	2.98	Agree
9.	Dry hair	2.56	2.84	2.70	Agree

X_1 = Mean of female adolescents between the ages of 12-18 years

X_2 = Mean of mothers (40-50)

X_g = grand Mean

Table 3 reveals the effect of poor nutrition on the hair of Adolescents and mothers. Mean responses on the respondents showed that all the items had a mean rating above 2.50 except item four. This means that the items on the effect of poor nutrition were identified.

Table 4: Mean rating on skills for hairdressers to enhance growth

S/N	Skills for hairdressers	X1	X2	Xg	Remarks
1.	Ability to determine the right hair texture	3.91	3.97	3.94	Agree
2.	Select the right relaxer	2.96	3.12	3.04	Agree
3.	Determine time of the relaxed hair	3.60	3.50	3.55	Agree
4.	Determine various hairstyles	3.42	2.98	3.21	Disagree
5.	Manipulate the hair drying equipment	2.61	3.22	2.94	Agree
6.	Know the operating procedure	2.56	3.36	2.96	Agree
7.	Fix suitable hair attachment	3.91	3.97	3.94	Agree
8.	Select correct hair combs and brushes	2.96	3.12	3.04	Agree
9.	Identify the cause of hair infection and treat it	3.42	2.98	3.20	Agree

10.	Clean and restyle of wigs	3.60	3.50	3.55	Agree
11.	Add ornaments to the hair	3.90	3.96	3.92	Agree
12.	Handle complaints with empathy	2.61	3.27	2.94	Agree

X_1 = Mean of female adolescents between the ages of 12-18 years

X_2 = Mean of mothers (40-50)

X_g = grand Mean

Table 4 presents the mean responses of adolescents and mothers on hairdressers skill related. A look at the table shows that selecting the right hair texture and fix suitable hair attachment has the highest grand mean score of 3.94. This indicates that both respondents are in agreement. As can be seen from the table, all the items had mean ratings above the cutoff point of 2.50.

The summary of the results are as follows:

- (a) Six items were agreed by the adolescent and mothers in promoting healthy hair.
- (b) Six items were equally agreed on the importance of human hair.
- (c) There are eight effects of poor nutrition on human hair. Dandruff was not agreed upon as effect of poor nutrition on human hair. Due to lipid loss, it makes hair dull, rough and neglected and not the effect of poor nutrition.
- (d) Furthermore, eleven items are highly agreed upon by the respondents as hair dressers skills. One of them is disagreed and it is determine various hair styles. According to Jablonski (2013) these hair styling can groom one's hair with the latest hair styles.

The result of the study reveals six items that promote human hair growth. To promote human hair growth the following should be taken into consideration which includes; take plenty of fruits and vegetables, maintain restful sleep, live a healthy life style, apply a good hair cream. More so, the result of the study revealed the six items that were regarded as the importance of human hair which add height, indicate taste, shows the state of health, and shows personality of an individual. Body heat is lost through the scalp and wearing hair can help reduce these loss, particularly in very cold spells. Hair is also kept to show beauty. This agrees with Steven, (2017) who said that people that really appear fashionable and beautiful endeavor to acquire only hair style that match them. Also, any outgoing person may over stricken hairstyle. David (2014) was of the opinion that people wear hairstyle to show class distinction and lifestyle. The hair itself reveals state of health due to lack of care. This is in agreement with Winden (2015) who reveals that if hair is not properly taken care of, a number of follicles diminish with age. When follicles are imprisoned in this way, hair production is stopped, hair density is reduced and remaining hair is strangled and compressed by the skin tension. Experts view that hair becomes thin and deformed.

Also, the result revealed 9 items in the effect of poor nutrition on the hair. These are thinning, falling, disappearing, dry hair. The findings were in conformity with Salako (2019) who said that poor nutrition result on falling hair and withered hair, among others. They are the hair diseases inherent due to poor nutrition guidelines. The findings agreed with Rodney (2016), who reasoned that for hair damages, severe scalp infection or hair loss diseases, it is recommended to use good quality shampoos that have enough moisturizing and nourishment properties. Ability to know the structure of the hair the importance of hair and the effect of poor nutrition on the hair makes one to know about the hair and what it takes to maintain it. Proper diet and healthy lifestyle coupled with right hair care products will result in lustrous hair. Further study shows hair dressers related skills.

The result revealed eleven out of twelve items discussed. Determine various hair styles was rejected for growth. This is because hair styling helps to create temporary changes in the hair volume and fibre. Ability to know the details of hair styling can be one of the best parts of any beauty regime. To throw more light, Jablonski (2013) said that these hair were divided into different zones and that these hair started by the down growth of thickened cells of the epidermis into the underlying dermis and connective tissue. Hair grow because of the continued division of these “matrix” cells. The scalp alone is covered with up to two million hairs growing about 0.3mm a day. Boulos et al. (2013) informed that the knowledge about the hair will help to guide on how to keep the hair shiny and healthy. Leena (2017) was of the opinion that the knowledge will help to guide what care to give to the hair to make it healthy. The findings were in agreement with Leena (2017) who stated that the method of acquiring skills and knowledge are through imitation, repetition and active participation of the skills. This agreed with Salako (2019) who complain that short, full styles that emphasize the upper face or styles with too much height at the crown should be avoided. It is hoped that if these skills are utilized, they will stand out stylist in the labour market and attract economy.

4. Conclusion

Females should endeavour to maintain their hair. It is one of the assets of an individual. Many people use it as a form of self-expression. To maintain the hair, a healthy supply of fruits and vegetables, whole grain and foods rich in calcium and protein are not only appealing but also highly nutritious. Take plenty of water. Alcohol should be among the first things to limit in one’s diet. Otherwise, hair thinning, falling, disappearing, hair damages, irreversible hair loss and severe scalp infection will result if hair is not maintained. The importance of human hair cannot be overemphasized. It beautifies one, shows the state of health. Also, ability to determine hair relaxer, fix suitable hair attachment are considered as hair dressers skills. Taking care of the hair restores colour, increases hair density, regains elasticity of the scalp and increases self-confidence of people. From the finding of the study it is therefore recommended that adolescents and mothers should always eat recommended diets to suit their age, they should maintain a good hairdresser and consult a dermatologist at regular intervals and keep his advice.

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None

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

PNE conceived and developed the research, wrote the paper, collected and analyzed the data.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed in this article can be obtained from the author on reasonable request. Further inquiries can be directed to the author.

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